

Manuals for the Sustainable Experience: How to keep Homo Ludens on the move

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Abstract

Homo Ludens is in danger. Modern Western society with its ready made notion of consumption makes it difficult for human beings to discover new worlds by themselves.

To keep playful man on the move, I am developing manuals for the sustainable experience. Behind this communication tool stands a line of products that are either produced by my company or by consumers. Their stories and experiences are collected as part of the project.

1- The travel experience

Typical is a collection of pictures showing culture by detail. Each cultural theme is presented by a collage. Tourists use Typical to communicate with local people. With the images they can speak about the culture they visit and about their own culture. This tool creates an atmosphere of give and take.

2- The erotic experience

The Erotic Story Box is a wooden container in which consumers can keep a collection of erotic images. When purchased the box is empty. With a transparent plastic template consumers can cut out images from books and magazines. Finally they can make their own erotic story line using a combination of exciting images.

3- The joyful experience

The washing machine drum is the basic ingredient for a cooking device. The drum can be connected to a tree with cables or put on a base of an old stool. The fire is fueled with wood refuse. Reuse of old products and burning of refuse guarantee a sustainable experience.

First Project: M069 Excite

Development Process, Tools and Methods

The way my concepts are developed can not be represented by a clear process because each new idea asks for a new approach. One element that is constantly being used though is the 'manual for the sustainable experience'. It is a presentation based on images and color bands that explain step by step and non-explicit how to achieve a certain experience. This tool is being used to communicate experiences to consumers. It functions as a clear addition to the product and explains the way the product can be used.

Contribution to User Experience & The Practice of Emotion-Driven Design

Emotion-driven design should not be aimed at specific emotions in consumers but instead come from the designer himself being in an intuitive state of mind in which he feels connected to all human beings.

Design Philosophy

To design ingredients for consumers to play with and to develop methods that explain how things *could* be done.

Description, Aims and Objectives

Description: A collection of erotic images which can be put together in a narrative collage.

Aim: The first aim is to make the largest erotic image library on earth. To achieve this a standard has been established. It measures 9 by 12 cm on paper or 150 by 200 pixels in digital format. All images are standing. A community of consumers is working together to build this archive. The second aim is to tell stories making use of the imagery. This is done by putting images together in a collage. The standard for both images and collages makes it possible for consumers to exchange images and storylines.

Objectives: To create erotic stories based on images and find ways to exchange these stories amongst users.

Results and Conclusions

Results: Since we have started this project, a group of 10 consumers is making use of the system. The archive is slowly growing and consumers involved are getting more conscious of eroticism. Either it be in themselves or in the world around them. A testcase in the botanical gardens of Amsterdam resulted in a collection of 40 stories made by 35 individuals. It was remarkable to see man and woman, young and old sitting at a large table making erotic collages. It even seemed to me that there is an erotic language based on images that both sexes like to look at. Another result is the use of images as an addition to loveletters. Images are also being send to friends to communicate certain thoughts.

Conclusions: It's too early to jump to concrete conclusions but it's clear that most users (especially woman) are sick and tired of pornography and willing to experiment with new concepts.

Market Segment

Erotic images and storylines.

Theoretical and Philosophical References

- Allende, I. (1998) "Aphrodite", London: Flamingo
Bennett, T. (2001) "Emotional Alchemy", New York: Harmony Books
Burton, R. (1885) "Kama Sutra", London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd
Heestermans, H. (1980) "Erotic dictionary", Utrecht: Prisma Books
Huizinga, J. (1950) "Homo Ludens", USA: Roy Publishers
Jensen, R. "The Dream Society", New York: McGraw-Hill
Nin, A. (1988) "Erotica, delta of Venus", Amsterdam: Bert Bakker
Paget, L. (2001) "The Big O", New York: Broadway Books.
Punja, S. (1992) "Divine Ecstasy, the story of Khajuraho", New Delhi: Penguin Books
Stubbs, K. (1998) "Secret sexual positions, ancient techniques for modern lovers", New York: Jeremy P. Tarcher/Putnam

Social, Cultural, Political and Educational Implications

Social: The existent commercial erotic language (i.e. pornography) is causing several social problems, one of which is that man and woman do not understand each others fantasies.

Pornography today is mostly very explicit and has storylines that are predictable, boring and woman-offensive.

Cultural: To find new, more poetic ways to tell erotic stories then the dominant Anglo-American way as can be found on most internet-sites, DVD movies and in erotic magazines.

Educational: To stimulate personal creativity as an alternative for the lazy consumer-attitude.

Second Project: M131 Exchange

Development Process, Tools and Methods

The way my concepts are developed can not be represented by a clear process because each new idea asks for a new approach. One element that is constantly being used though is the 'manual for the sustainable experience'. It is a presentation based on images and color bands that explain step by step and non-explicit how to achieve a certain experience. This tool is being used to communicate experiences to consumers. It functions as a clear addition to the product and explains the way the product can be used.

Contribution to User Experience & The Practice of Emotion-Driven Design

Emotion-driven design should not be aimed at specific emotions in consumers but instead come from the designer himself being in an intuitive state of mind in which he feels connected to all human beings.

Design Philosophy

To design ingredients for consumers to play with and to develop methods that explain how things *could* be done.

Description, Aims and Objectives

Description: M131 is a collection of pictures showing culture by detail. Each cultural theme is presented by a collage. Tourists use this concept to communicate with local people. With the images they can speak about the culture they visit and about their own culture.

Aim: To create a sustainable relationship between tourists and locals based on give and take.

Objectives: To bring together a large group of photographers that are willing to collect images of culture on the spot. These images are brought together on a website where visitors can browse by country. All images will be published in small travel books for tourists to bring along.

Results and Conclusions

Results: Around eight countries are present on the website so far, with an average of three themes per country. Three photographers have been working with the concept. A couple of travellers have been using prints of images whilst having contact with locals. Cards were also given as a present and have sometimes led to new stories and even friendships.

Conclusions: This communication tool serves as a way to come closer to locals and creates an atmosphere of understanding and exchange of cultural information.

Market Segment

Sustainable tourism.

Theoretical and Philosophical References

Huizinga, J. (1950) "Homo Ludens", USA: Roy Publishers

Jensen, R. "The Dream Society", New York: McGraw-Hill

Pine J. & Gilmore J.H. (1999) "The experience economy", Boston: Harvard Business School Press

Rifkin, J. (2000) "The age of Access", New York: Jeremy P. Tarcher/Putnam

Social, Cultural, Political and Educational Implications

Social: A better, more profound contact between tourist and local.

Cultural: Exchange of cultural information by telling stories.

Educational: Unlike the one-dimensional view of the resort-tourist on culture, this concept creates a situation of give and take in which *both* parties learn from one another.

M069 EXCITE | EXCITAR | EXCITER | AUFREGEN | EXCITAR | OPWINDEN |

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Figure 1, Manual M069 for a sustainable experience. Design by Daisy Erades and The Moment Company, 2004.